

Key Features of a Successful Girls' Afterschool STEM Program

Participant Insights 30 Years Later

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Out-of-school learning contexts provide rich opportunities for authentic and experiential learning, connecting learners with real-world experiences and allowing them to explore socialization into their collective identities, such as gender, race, and the intersection of the two (e.g., Cooper, 2011). However, one challenge lies in the variability of informal educators' expertise and vision. The qualifications and experience of informal educators can vary widely, and limited research exists on their professional competencies, the pedagogical approaches they use, or the long-term vision they bring to programs (Allen & Crowley, 2014; Jeffs & Smith, 2021).

Afterschool science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) programs often include interventions such as exposure to role models, hands-on activities, and single-sex learning environments to foster learners' interest in STEM (e.g., Ennes et al., 2020; Holmes et al., 2012; King & Pringle, 2019). Research has shown that participation in these programs can effectively boost students' interest and confidence in STEM subjects (e.g., Chen et al., 2011; Chittum et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2025).

Despite the success of informal STEM programs, one ongoing challenge is sustaining learners' interest beyond the programs' initial impact (Morris et al., 2019). Although some longitudinal studies suggest

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that such programs can have a lasting impact on girls in STEM (e.g., McCreedy & Dierking, 2013), further research is needed to identify the distinctive features of successful programs that create meaningful and enduring change.

The present study seeks to address this gap with a retrospective exploration of the experiences of the first cohort of participants in a longstanding girls' STEM program, Girls Excelling in Math and Science (GEMS). In interviews and focus groups, women now in their 40s described their experiences in the program 30 years ago. The study is guided by the research question: *What distinctive features of GEMS as an informal learning environment emerge from the retrospective narratives of the original participants?* Guided by sociocultural theory, I used thematic analysis to unpack participants' narratives to reveal three key features of the program. The study provides actionable insights for designing effective afterschool programs and informal learning opportunities to engage girls and learners from historically underrepresented communities in STEM fields.

Sociocultural Theoretical Perspective

The study is framed by Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, which emphasizes the social environment as a facilitator of development and learning. Vygotsky (1978) recognized the importance of instruction and assistance in learning and viewed instruction as a social practice to guide learning. Sociocultural learning theory emphasizes social participation, collective learning, and culturally relevant activities.

Building on Vygotsky's work, Rogoff (1990) expanded the understanding of teacher-student communication by incorporating emotional and nonverbal forms of interaction, exchanging daily life experiences, and engaging students in personally relevant activities. Rogoff introduced the concept of "guided participation," where adults or peers challenge, constrain, and support children in posing and solving problems. This process involves both interpersonal communication and material arrangements of activities and responsibilities. In addition to interpersonal interactions, Leont'ev

(1974) emphasized the importance of interactions with activities themselves. Participation in activities mediates students' cognitive development, shapes their learning processes, and determines their outcomes.

The sociocultural theory underscores the critical role of both interpersonal and activity-based interactions in fostering meaningful learning experiences. Guided by sociocultural theory, this study seeks to explore the features of GEMS as a learning environment that fostered social interactions and engaged students through various activities. By analyzing participants' reflections and past experiences, the study explores how these features contributed to the program's long-term impacts. Retrospective accounts offer a unique lens for understanding how social and cultural factors shape learning over time, providing insights that may not be immediately visible in real-time observations. This approach aligns with sociocultural theory by capturing how learners interpret and make meaning of past interactions.

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Context

Girls Excelling in Math and Science (GEMS) is an informal STEM program initiated in 1994 by a mother, Laura Jones, and her daughter's teacher, Ms. Cooper (a pseudonym), with the goal of fostering girls' confidence in mathematics and science. In GEMS's inaugural year (1994–1995), more than 40 fifth- and sixth-grade girls joined the program through teacher recommendations, parental requests, or voluntary enrollment. As the program's leaders, Laura and Ms. Cooper attended educational workshops, sought out professional development opportunities, and explored resources from the internet and library. Besides using existing activities like Möbius strips and chromatography, they also developed their own activities, such as coding, designing mazes, dyeing shirts, and more (Jones, 2002a, 2002b). Over time, they added more science, engineering, and technology activities.

Laura completed two reports, in 1997 and 2002, to examine the impact of the GEMS on the original GEMS girls (OGGs) who attended during the inaugural year. The findings from both reports were

documented in her unpublished thesis (Jones, 2002a). The first report, in 1997, focused on feedback from girls, parents, and classroom teachers. The results were positive and encouraging; teachers noted increased interest in math and science among the girls. The second report, in 2002, investigated the OGGs' high school course selections and career interests. A survey of 41 OGGs showed that the OGGs were more likely than their peers to enroll in advanced technology, mathematics, and science courses.

Laura's unpublished reports serve as a foundational reference for this study. My study shifts focus from evaluating outcomes to understanding the OGGs' experiences with GEMS as a learning environment. It delves into the OGGs' retrospective narratives, exploring what they remember about their participation and how they interpret those experiences as adults.

Methods

In 2018, Laura partnered with my doctoral institution to expand GEMS's reach. As a research assistant, I collaborated with Laura to establish new GEMS clubs, design activities, and conduct program-related research (Zhou, 2024). This article is part of a larger project aimed at examining the long-term impacts of GEMS on its participants.

Participants and Data Sources

With assistance from Laura and her daughter Janet, who is an OGG, 25 OGGs were invited to participate in our survey. The survey asked about respondents' educational backgrounds, careers, and memories related to GEMS, among other aspects. Seventeen OGGs responded to the survey, but three surveys were left incomplete. Of the 14 OGGs who completed the survey, 12 identified as White, one as White and Black or African American, and another as White and Hispanic or Latinx. All participants in this study are identified by pseudonyms.

All 14 OGGs had completed a college degree; six held master's degrees, and one held a doctoral degree. Four of the 14 OGGs had pursued STEM majors at some point, while 10 had not. Two of the 14 participants were currently working in STEM fields; the remaining 12 individuals did not mention any STEM-related experience. Additionally, 10 of the 14 OGGs reported that they were mothers.

Nine OGGs, all of whom identified as White,

participated in subsequent interviews. I grouped participants by common experiences from survey responses: working in the same field or being a mom. The result was three focus groups consisting of four, three, and two OGGs. The focus group interviews had three goals: introduce the study purpose, establish rapport and trust, and provide an opportunity for the OGGs to recall collective GEMS memories. Following the focus groups, semi-structured individual interviews were conducted with the nine OGGs. We used insights from the focus groups to tailor questions to individual participants in order to prompt their memories. The questions adapted and grew through dynamic exchanges during the interviews.

Data Analysis

This study employed thematic analysis to explore participants' retrospective narratives (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Clandinin & Connelly, 2000). Using sociocultural theory as the guiding framework emphasizes the critical role of interpersonal interactions, activities, and cultural contexts in shaping learning experiences. This framework informed the coding process and interpretation of themes, enabling a deep understanding of GEMS as a learning environment.

The analysis process consisted of three stages. First, I carefully reviewed both the survey and interview data to identify information relevant to participants' experiences in GEMS. In the second stage, I conducted an iterative coding process, categorizing the data into meaningful units and identifying patterns that emerged organically from the data. This inductive, data-driven approach ensured that themes reflected OGGs' authentic experiences. In the third stage, guided by a sociocultural theoretical perspective, I synthesized the identified patterns into overarching themes, offering a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences of GEMS.

Outstanding Features of GEMS

The analysis of participants' retrospective narratives, guided by sociocultural theory, revealed three key features of GEMS: social engagement as a foundation for learning, activities as a catalyst for learning, and the enduring influence of GEMS. These features, which remain as relevant now as they were 30 years ago, provide valuable insights for today's afterschool initiatives.

Social Engagement as a Foundation for Learning

Social engagement was a foundation of the GEMS program, fostering a supportive and inspiring environment that empowered participants and enhanced their learning experiences. Through meaningful interactions with leaders and peers, participants built confidence, curiosity, and a sense of belonging.

Inspiring Leaders

Laura took the initiative to establish GEMS with the primary goal of supporting her daughter, Janet, and other girls in learning mathematics and science. Laura's dedication to GEMS spanned an impressive 30-plus years. Janet recalled how her mother played a pivotal role in creating GEMS, providing a comfortable and nurturing environment:

I think it started when [Laura] took me to a magnet school, and I told her that math was hard. I don't remember all the details, but suddenly she was creating this math and science club for girls. For me, it just felt natural—I went along with it, and it gave me more time to spend with my mom and my friends.

Janet's teacher, Ms. Cooper, collaborated with Laura as a co-leader of GEMS. Many OGGs shared that they chose to participate in GEMS specifically because of Ms. Cooper. May said:

Ms. Cooper was my favorite teacher—her enthusiasm for every lesson or activity made learning exciting. She had such a love for the subject that it made you feel excited too. I still remember how she always brought pie on Pi Day!

Cassy added, "Ms. Cooper helped us to learn. She taught in ways that helped almost every student understand." Stella expressed appreciation for Ms. Cooper's teaching style: "Ms. Cooper was a visual storyteller. When she taught math and science, she used visuals a lot."

Creating an engaging learning environment like

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GEMS requires strong leadership. Effective leaders must have a clear vision to set specific goals, ensuring that activities and initiatives align with the program's objectives. Moreover, the GEMS leaders' expertise in pedagogy and understanding of student dynamics not only guided the content but also inspired a passion for learning among participants.

Supportive Peer Community

GEMS created a safe and inclusive environment that fostered collaboration, friendship, and

personal growth among its participants. The girls-only setting allowed OGGs to freely express their thoughts, ask questions, and share their perspectives without fear of judgment. Many OGGs cherished the experience. In interviews, they emphasized the importance of the girls-only environment, which provided a supportive and understanding space in their pre-teen years:

- "I remember being with my friends and having so much fun."
- "I do remember laughing with my friends every week."
- "I especially loved GEMS because my best friend ... went too."

For some, GEMS served as a much-needed refuge. Cindy reflected, "I just remember it being such a positive environment.... Sixth grade was my year of a bully, and this was a safe space for me to interact with positive girls." The absence of boys contributed to a relaxed and pressure-free environment. Elli explained:

There were no boys, which made a big difference. In sixth grade, that's often when you start worrying about what others think and don't want to answer questions for fear of looking stupid. GEMS felt like a much more relaxed environment, where girls didn't have to deal with that kind of pressure.

May contrasted GEMS with traditional classrooms, sharing:

I felt more comfortable and participated more in GEMS than in a classroom setting. The hands-on, no-grades environment made it fun and relaxed, unlike in class,

where I often kept answers to myself out of fear of being wrong. As a child, those fears are a big deal.

By offering a judgment-free and supportive peer community, GEMS provided the girls with a safe space to build social skills, form meaningful friendships, and gain confidence in learning.

Activities as a Catalyst for Learning

According to Jones (2002a, 2002b) and the OGGs' descriptions, GEMS offered experiments, projects, and activities. OGGs recalled many memorable activities, such as constructing bridges with gumdrops and toothpicks, creating volcanoes with baking soda and vinegar, designing shirts with alcohol and markers, dissecting owl pellets, estimating candy quantities in containers, engaging in simulated stock market activities, and launching rockets fueled by a combination of vinegar and a common heartburn remedy. The activities worked as a catalyst for learning; OGGs described learning through activities as experiential and enjoyable. In addition, hands-on activities provided the OGGs with the opportunity to collaborate. The assessment of these activities differed from traditional classroom assessments, relying primarily on participants' reflections and group discussions.

Experiential Activities

As OGGs recalled their experience in GEMS, they frequently used the words *excited*, *fun*, *interesting*, and *engaging* to describe activities, for example:

- "I enjoyed the freedom of kind of playing around—to see what would happen."
- "These activities were fun and entertaining."
- "I remember the feeling of being excited about the activities."
- "I remember enjoying the activities very much and being excited about learning because the activities made it fun!"

May vividly described her complex feelings about GEMS activities:

I was always excited to dive into a science experiment or math activity. Although I was a bit shy in large groups, I was eager to get started. The leaders would give instruc-

tions, and I'd rush over with a mix of anticipation, nervousness, and excitement all swirling together.

Paige elaborated on how the experiential learning in GEMS drew on knowledge gained in school to make connections with real life:

My math and science experiences in GEMS were more experiential and applied compared to school, where math was mostly about solving problems. GEMS connected those skills to real-world activities, showing their importance and the kinds of problems they could help solve.

OGGs said that the activities in GEMS provided enjoyable learning experiences. These activities empowered the OGGs to become more confident in learning and cultivated their interests in STEM subjects.

Learning without Pressure

The OGGs particularly cherished the noncompetitive and judgment-free environment of GEMS, where there were no grades, no right or wrong answers, and no judgment from other students or teachers. Learning was not driven by the pursuit of grades or competition; rather, it was about the experience, fostering a sense of enjoyment rather than fear of failure. OGGs said:

- "It just felt like a space where we didn't have to worry if our answer was wrong, or something didn't quite work."
- "You can ask questions. There was definitely no stupid question."
- "There's no grade [in GEMS]. You don't fail, you're not yelled at. We're going to just learn this thing for fun."
- "I feel the pressure went away because there wasn't a right or wrong answer—no one was grading."

Jess described learning without pressure: "It seemed like play, but you were learning at the same time. It was a lot more comfortable and relaxed because you didn't realize you were learning." Lynda commented, "When you allow kids to learn for the sake of learning, it becomes a completely different

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experience.” Elli shared, “The hands-on aspect helped me understand concepts better than in a traditional setting of books and tests. You could see how things worked for yourself and understand concepts while enjoying yourself.” Lynda added, “It’s not just about reading from a textbook—it’s more like, ‘Set off the volcano and explain why baking soda reacts this way.’” GEMS incorporated hands-on and experiential learning, providing the OGGs with the opportunity to participate actively in their learning.

Enduring Influence of GEMS

Reflecting on their experiences in GEMS over 30 years ago, the OGGs shared how the program left a lasting impression on their lives. They identified several long-term impacts, including significant contributions to their personal growth, career choices, and ongoing perspectives on gender equity in STEM.

Building Confidence

The OGGs noted that GEMS changed them as individuals. One OGG stated, “I do believe it gave me more generalized confidence in my math abilities.” Another added, “GEMS helped me realize my potential.” Elli expressed, “Although I didn’t go into a math or science field, I believe that was an opportunity as a young girl to do something outside of my comfort zone.”

Several OGGs shared how GEMS reshaped their perceptions of their abilities, particularly in mathematics. Stella, for instance, struggled with mathematics before GEMS. “I had always been awful at math,” she said. “GEMS made me think that math wasn’t as scary. I learned that I understood applied math in a way that I didn’t get from memorizing times tables.” Stella attributed her career choice, which allows her to merge her passion for sciences with her natural communication abilities, to the encouragement she received at GEMS:

I think GEMS had a huge impact on encouraging people because, prior to GEMS, I had assumed, based on my past performance, that I would be a writer or something like that. I ended up in the technical world, where I

could merge both my love of the sciences and my natural communication abilities.

These reflections underscore the long-term impact of GEMS, demonstrating how the program nurtured participants’ confidence, broadened their perspectives, and influenced their personal and professional lives.

Inspiring the Next Generation of Girls in STEM

The impact of GEMS extends far beyond the original participants, as many OGGs have carried the program’s commitment to empowering girls and women into their present lives and attitudes. Although only a small number of OGGs entered STEM fields, their experiences in GEMS have had a profound influence on many OGGs’ attitudes toward gender equity and STEM education. For instance, Kate shared that the confidence she built in GEMS enabled her to feel comfortable even in male-dominated college courses. Another OGG reflected, “I am very mindful of gender stereotypes and how they impact females’ beliefs about themselves and their abilities in math and science.” This awareness demonstrates how GEMS inspired participants to challenge societal norms and support gender equity in STEM.

Janet’s involvement with GEMS went beyond her years as a participant. She later assumed a leadership role, sharing, “I left GEMS when I was in middle school. In high school, I would come back to help with activities as well as lead a session or two at the yearly conferences.”

Stella actively contributes to supporting girls in science through professional mentoring and volunteering. She shared:

I give back a lot to girls in the sciences. I also spend a lot of time professionally mentoring girls in science. I volunteer with Girls Who Code to teach girls how to code. We have an organization at our company called Built by Girls that does a lot of outreach work for women in STEM.

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Stella’s dedication exemplifies how the values instilled in GEMS continue to inspire outreach and advocacy for women in STEM fields.

Additionally, many OGGs, now mothers, expressed a desire to provide their children, especially daughters, with opportunities similar to those they experienced in GEMS. Paige shared how the program inspired her to actively engage her daughter in STEM-related subjects: “I role-play a broad range of jobs with my daughter as well—astronauts, doctors, architects, in addition to family, princess, et cetera. I will be actively seeking out opportunities to engage her in these subjects as she grows older.”

Practical Implications

This study highlights the enduring impact of GEMS on its participants, particularly in fostering confidence, nurturing interest in STEM, and promoting gender equity. The findings not only emphasize the unique features of GEMS but also offer practical suggestions for designing effective afterschool programs and informal learning opportunities to engage students in STEM fields. By drawing on sociocultural theory, this study underscores the role of relationships and hands-on activities in shaping participants’ STEM engagement and learning experiences.

Creating Supportive and Inclusive Environments

One of the key features of GEMS was its ability to create a supportive and inclusive environment through social engagement, where participants felt safe to express themselves and collaborate without fear of judgment. The girls-only setting played a pivotal role in fostering this sense of belonging, enabling participants to build confidence while inspiring meaningful learning. These insights align with previous literature suggesting that afterschool programs can benefit from establishing environments that are free from competition and promote collaboration (Cooper, 2011). Afterschool and informal learning initiatives that design spaces to prioritize emotional safety and inclusivity reduce stresses that can hinder participation, particularly for underrepresented groups. Moreover, single-gender or small-group settings like GEMS, especially in STEM fields, encourage active participation and mitigate societal stereotypes.

Passionate and supportive

leaders are central to the success of informal STEM programs (Allen & Crowley, 2014; Jeffs & Smith, 2021). In GEMS, Ms. Cooper and Laura played a crucial role in designing the program, connecting with participants and tailoring teaching approaches to meet diverse learning needs. Other informal learning contexts can replicate this success by training informal educators and mentors to adopt culturally responsive teaching practices and foster sustained engagement for STEM learners.

Emphasizing Experiential and Hands-On Learning

Research consistently highlights the importance of experiential, hands-on activities in making learning enjoyable and relevant (Morris et al., 2019). Activities such as building models, conducting experiments, and simulating real-world scenarios help participants connect classroom learning to tangible applications (Chittum et al., 2017). GEMS’s experiential approach not only deepened understanding but also cultivated curiosity and enjoyment, making the subjects accessible and exciting.

Consistent with previous studies (Ennes et al., 2020; Holmes et al., 2012; King & Pringle, 2019), the OGGs’ retrospective reflections on their GEMS experiences highlight the importance of prioritizing hands-on, project-based activities in afterschool and informal programs to connect STEM concepts with real-world problems and applications. Collaborative tasks can enhance teamwork skills and foster meaningful social connections among participants. Additionally, moving beyond traditional assessments by using reflections, self-reporting, or group discussions can enable evaluation of learning in a low-pressure and supportive environment.

Fostering Long-Term Impact and Advocacy

The long-term influence of GEMS is evident in participants’ personal and professional lives and their dedication to advancing gender equity in STEM. Examples like Janet and Stella demonstrate how mentorship can create a cycle of empowerment, enabling participants to

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become advocates and role models for others. Many participants carried the values instilled by GEMS into their careers, parenting, and advocacy efforts, highlighting the potential for informal learning programs to spark enduring change. This study highlights the importance of creating opportunities for participants to see themselves as doers and active contributors to STEM fields.

To maximize the long-term impact of informal learning, programs must encourage participants to take leadership roles, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility. Programs should also provide opportunities for participants to connect their in-school and out-of-school mathematics experiences, fostering a more integrated understanding of the subject and reinforcing its relevance to their lives (Zhou et al., 2025). Furthermore, incorporating elements that challenge societal norms and stereotypes can promote confidence and resilience, especially among underrepresented groups in STEM (Chittum et al., 2017).

Advancing Equity in STEM

GEMS demonstrates that informal learning environments can serve as critical spaces for engaging underrepresented populations in STEM. Drawing from participants' retrospective experiences over 30 years, this study's findings show that GEMS fostered confidence, curiosity, and a sense of belonging. This work illustrates the potential of supportive and inclusive programs to address systemic barriers that often hinder participation in STEM for students from historically underserved communities.

The study provides practical guidance to help educators and program leaders design equitable and impactful informal learning experiences. By reflecting on the long-term influence of GEMS on participants' personal growth, professional paths, and advocacy efforts, this study underscores the importance of creating programs that empower learners and contribute to a more diverse and equitable STEM community.

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